

Integrated multiproduct facility for the production of chemicals, food and utilities from oranges.

Arantza Criado, Mariano Martín*

Departamento de Ingeniería Química. Universidad de Salamanca. Pza. Caídos 1-5, 37008 Salamanca (Spain)

Abstract.

An integrated facility for the processing of oranges is designed. The process begins with juice production. From the peel, two pretreatments are considered for the production of limonene, steam explosion and solvent extraction. Next, the waste is digested to produce utilities and fertilizers. The flue gas from the gas turbine can either be used to produce electricity in a regenerative Rankine cycle or as utility for the process. A process systems approach is used to analyse alternative technologies and estimate the economics. The use of steam explosion requires 50% lower production costs but 30% higher investment to treat the waste. The use of hexane consumes 4 times more thermal energy but the processing of the waste requires less digesters. Combined cycles are less profitable. The lower production cost of the steam explosion allows for smaller facilities to become profitable before the ones using hexane limonene recovery.

Keywords: Oranges, Anaerobic digestion, Integrated facility, Added value products, Mathematical optimization

1.- Introduction

Food is one of the three main pillars of the water-energy-food (WEF) nexus. The links among the three are responsible for the sustainability of society.¹ Water is needed for both the production of energy and food, energy is needed for water treatment and food production and so on.² While this nexus is a current trend

* Corresponding autor M. Martín: mariano.m3@usal.es

analyzed and implemented in the chemical and power industries,³ food production companies are product oriented,⁴ that do not typically work as chemical complexes. However, a more integrated analysis can allow energy savings improving the sustainability and the economics of the facility. Food waste is attracting attention lately due to the large volumes generated.⁵ By integrating the residues in the case of citrics⁶ or other food wastes,⁷ it is possible not only to produce added value chemicals, but also to reduce the consumption of utilities while managing and valorizing the waste generated in their operation. By reusing the waste, the principles of circular economy are implemented within the food industry. For the particular case of processing fruit to produce juice, peels are also produced.⁸ This residue contains certain compounds of high added value such as pectin⁹ or limonene¹⁰ that can be obtained towards a more integrated process design and total waste valorisation.¹¹

Anaerobic Digestion (AD) provides an alternative to process the waste and close the cycle. Different fruits have been evaluated for biogas production.^{12,13} The main products from the AD of waste consist of biogas, composed of CO₂ and CH₄ that can be an interesting source for chemicals via dry reforming¹⁴ or power,¹⁵ and a digestate rich in nutrients that can be recovered in different forms.¹⁶ For the case of the food industry and, in particular, of the fruit industry, strategies for a cleaner production have been presented aiming at reducing the CO₂ emissions.¹⁷ However, studies have evaluated different parts of the process separately. The digestion of citrus waste has been evaluated to estimate the yield to biogas,¹⁸ while the mixture of peels and waste water from citrus facilities has also been studied,¹⁹ evaluating the yield and the kinetics. However, before processing the waste, high added value products can be obtained²⁰ such as essential oils.²¹ Limonene can be produced from microorganisms but it is typically obtained from citrus wastes via extraction.²² Pectin can be recovered from the hydrolysis of the peel.⁹ The analysis of waste refineries has been presented lately using simulation approaches including the process of the fruit to produce limonene,⁶ the use of limonene to produce p-Cymene and the recovery of pectin²³ including the possible use of the waste to produce power via gasification. The large water content within the waste and the need to determine the optimal integration suggest the use of optimization techniques for the design of integrated polygeneration facilities within the food industry that go beyond typical approaches where bulk chemicals and power were obtained from lignocellulosic biomass and solar energy,²⁴ using hybrid fossil-biomass based facilities²⁵ or integrating hybrid solar & waste.²⁶

In this work the circular economy concepts are applied to the fruit industry by developing an integrated facility to produce juice, high added value chemicals, limonene, power as well as fertilizer to be used back in the

field from oranges using a mathematical optimization formulation. The rest of the paper is organized in four sections. Section 2 depicts the integrated process. Section 3 presents the modelling assumptions of the units involved in the flowsheet and the cost estimation procedure. In section 4, the results are discussed including the selection among alternative technologies and the results of the economic evaluation. Finally, in section 5, some conclusions are presented

2.- Process description

The process can be divided into five stages. The first one processes fruit to extract the juice using a screw. The juice must be pasteurized before storage or packing. From the peels, limonene is extracted. Two different technologies are considered such as the use of hexane or steam explosion. Next the limonene is purified. In the case of using hexane, it is put into contact with the milled peels, centrifuged and the hexane is recovered in a stripping column. The hexane is condensed and recycled. The steam explosion pretreatment consists of feeding steam to a batch tank where the milled biomass is put into contact with steam. After a few minutes, the pressure is released and the limonene together with water is evaporated. The rest of the water and the residual biomass are sent to anaerobic digestion.

From the digester onwards, the facility is a power plant. At the digester, biogas and fertilizer are produced. The biogas contains small quantities of chemicals such as H_2S , NH_3 that must be removed before use. After biogas clean-up, two alternatives are considered, either the use of a combined cycle, where first a Brayton cycle is used to produce electricity from the biogas and, in a second stage, the hot flue gas is used to generate steam to feed the steam turbine and generate electricity. This alternative reduces water cooling needs per kW produced.²⁷ A second alternative consists of the use of the hot flue gas to produce thermal energy to help self-sustain the operation of the facility. Figure 1 shows a scheme of the superstructure.

Figure 1.-Integrated facility for food, chemicals and power production

3.- Modelling issues

The units involved in the process are modelled based on first principles to evaluate their performance. Mass and energy balances are used for all units while the compressors and turbines required thermodynamic data. In addition, either based on experimental data or first principles, distillation columns and solvent extractions are modelled using vapor-liquid equilibria.²⁸ For the digester as well as mechanical equipment such as mills, experimental data for the yields and power consumption are used. The model variables are the flows, total and component mass, their composition, mass fractions, and their temperatures and pressures. The components considered are within the set { H_2O , CO_2 , CO , O_2 , N_2 , H_2S , NH_3 , CH_4 , SO_2 , C , H , O , N , Norg , P , K , S , Rest , WON , P_2O_5 , K_2O , Oranges , Juice , Hexane , Limonene }. Over the next subsections the basics for the models of the different units are detailed. For the sake of the length of the paper, units modelled in previous works are either detailed in the supplementary material or just referenced.

3.1.- Oranges reception

The juice oranges are received at the facility. It is assumed that 50% of the mass is peel and the rest is juice with pulp. It is also considered that the pulp is part of the juice too. The oranges are washed using 2L of water per kg of orange, see Figure 2. This water is sent to treatment before reuse. It is assumed that the oranges do not carry washing water to the next unit. This washing stage is modelled using simple mass balances. Next, the oranges are squeezed. The milling process consumes 3.6 $\text{kJ}_e/\text{kg Peel}$.²⁹ The juice must be pasteurized in two steps removing microorganisms and denaturalizing enzymes. The first stage consists of heating the juice up to 368 K for 10-30 s. After that, and before bottling it up, the juice is heated up again for 15 s to 368 K.³⁰

3.2.-Peel processing

There are a number of technologies that allow recovering limonene out of orange peels. The amount of essential oils in the peel is around 1-1.3% by weight, of which 90% corresponds to limonene.^{23,31} Among the technologies, the most used are the extraction with solvents, in particular hexane,³² steam explosion or hydro-distillation.³³ From the two ones using water, hydro distillation only achieves 77% removal versus the almost 100% in case of using steam explosion.³³ The advantage of recovering limonene from the peels is, apart from the additional income, the improvement in the biogas production yield.³²

3.2.1.- Hexane extraction.

Limonene, d-limonene, can be recovered from the peel by extraction. The peel must be milled to increase the surface area. Next, n-hexane is used to extract it. A hexane to organic matter ratio of 12 : 1 is fed to the extractor. Hexane is capable of recovering 0.55 dm³ per m³ used.³² The peel residue is separated by filtration and it is sent to the digester. The liquid phase is distilled to recover the solvent. Unlike previous work³⁴ a stripping column is to be used due to the large difference in boiling points between limonene and hexane. The column is modelled based on first principles. The feed enters the column as saturated liquid computed using the vapor pressure of both the hexane and the limonene. Over the top, hexane as saturated vapour is recovered. Limonene comes out of the bottoms almost pure as saturated liquid. The hexane must be condensed and cooled down before recycling it. See Figure 2 for a scheme of this section.

Figure 2.- Scheme of the production of juice and limonene via hexane extraction

3.2.2.-Steam explosion

The slurry of peels is fed to a reactor with 10% solids.²² It is heated up with steam up to 150 °C and 15 bar. The reactor is open so that the liquid is evaporated, breaking down the biomass and extracting the limonene

together with evaporated water. The essential oil represents 1.1% of the orange peels of which 90% corresponds to limonene.³³ It is assumed that 90% of the limonene can be recovered. After the expansion, both streams are at 100°C. The solid-liquid phase is cooled down to the digestion temperature. The vapor phase contains the limonene. It is condensed in a heat exchanger so that the limonene is recovered in a liquid - liquid separation,²² see Figure 3.

Figure 3.-Scheme of the steam explosion recovery of limonene.

3.3.-Anaerobic digestion.

The treated peels are fed to the digester,³⁵ see Figure 4 for the scheme of this section. As such its composition is given by Table 1. However, in case additional water accompanies the peels the dry matter, wDM, decreases. It is possible to process a mixture with around 20% dry matter due to mixing issues. The digestion of the peels yields a biogas consisting of CH₄, CO₂, and traces of NH₃, H₂S, N₂ and O₂. The rest goes to the digestate. The biogas composition and flow are computed considering the biogas yield from the biomass, see Table 1, and performing a mass balance to the carbon, the organic and inorganic nitrogen, the phosphorous, the potassium. The detailed balance can be found in previous work.¹⁵

The digestate consists of the residue that remains after the production of the biogas. Before it can be used as fertilizer, water and ammonia must be evaporated. The features of any fertilizer are given by its NPK index, that corresponds to the fraction of nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) in the residue. For the fertilizer to be sold, it must meet the following ratios, eq. (1):

$$K_{index} + N_{index} + P_{index} \geq 6\%$$

$$0 \leq R_{C-N/fertilizer} = \frac{fc(C)}{fc(Norg)} \leq 20 \quad (1)$$

Table 1.—Orange peels composition for digestion ¹⁸

V _{biogas} (m ³ /kg)	0.35
W _{DM}	0.21
W _{VS}	0.85
W _{Nam}	0.002
W _{Norg}	0.010
W _P	0.002
W _K	0.009
R _{CN}	15

Figure 4.- Waste digestion into biogas and digestate

3.4.-Power cycle

The biogas has to be treated before it can be used. The H₂S is removed in a fixed-bed reactor operating at 55 °C and 4.5 bar that uses Fe₂O₃ as reactive bed as follows:

Thus, the biogas is compressed before being fed to the packed bed. Next, NH₃ and CO₂ are removed. The same unit is used for both since the amount of NH₃ is at the level of traces. The operating conditions are 25°C

and 4.5 bar. The type of adsorbent bed is zeolite 5A. Two beds operate in parallel to maintain continuous operation so that while one is in adsorbing mode, the second one is being regenerated. The amounts of NH₃ and H₂O to be removed are in the level of traces, therefore complete removal at the bed is assumed. In addition, the PSA system is assumed to remove 95 % of the CO₂ but no other species of the biogas mixture.

3.4.1.-Gas turbine.

The gas turbine or the Brayton cycle is modelled consisting of three stages such as air and biomethane compression, the combustion chamber and the gas expansion.¹⁵ The feed compression consists of a multistage compression stage with intercooling. The compressor efficiency is assumed to be 85 %.³⁶ The polytropic coefficient, k , is computed offline using CHEMCAD® and turns out to be 1.4.

$$T_{out/compressor} = T_{in/compressor} + T_{in/compressor} \left(\left(\frac{P_{out/compressor}}{P_{in/compressor}} \right)^{\frac{k-1}{k}} - 1 \right) \frac{1}{\eta_c} \quad (2)$$

$$W_{(Compressor)} = (F) \frac{R \cdot k \cdot (T_{in/compressor})}{((MW) \cdot (k-1))} \frac{1}{\eta_c} \left(\left(\frac{P_{out/compressor}}{P_{in/compressor}} \right)^{\frac{k-1}{k}} - 1 \right) \quad (3)$$

The combustion chamber is modelled assuming adiabatic operation. The flue gas is expanded assuming polytropic behaviour, with a coefficient k equal to 1.3, validated with a rigorous process simulator, and an efficiency of 0.85. The main operating variables correspond to the inlet and outlet pressure and the excess of air.

3.4.2.-Steam turbine.

A three-stage steam turbine consisting of high, medium and low pressure turbines is considered. Based on previous work,¹⁵ the steam generation uses the full hot flue gas to produce saturated steam that is fed it to the high-pressure turbine. The flue gas is further used as heating agent to reheat the expanded steam before feeding it to the medium pressure turbine. A fraction of the steam is used to represent the extractions in power plants that are used to reheat up the condensate. It is assumed that it is medium pressure steam. The rest is sent to the low pressure turbine for the final expansion. Each of the steam expansions are modelled similarly. The steam enthalpy and entropy are correlated as a function of its pressure and the temperature. The modeling approach

and the expressions can be found in previous works.^{15,37} To compute the steam exiting any of the three turbines an isentropic efficiency, η_s , of 0.9, is assumed where

$$\eta_s = \frac{H_{steam-out} - H_{steam-in}}{H_{steam-isentropic} - H_{steam-in}} \quad (4)$$

Where

$$H_{steam-isentropic} = f(p_{out}, T_{S,out}) \quad (5)$$

Where $T_{S,out}$ is the isentropic temperature after the expansion computed using eq. (6):

$$s_{steam,in} = f(p_{in}, T_{in}) = f(p_{out}, T_{S,out}) \quad (6)$$

The stream exiting each turbine has to be superheated. To ensure that, its temperature must be above the saturated temperature given by the Antoine correlation for that pressure. Only the extraction of the low pressure turbine is allowed to be saturated. Thus, for each expansion, the power obtained is computed as follows:

$$W_{(Turbine)} = f_{c,steam} \cdot (H_{Steam-in} - H_{Steam-out}) \quad (7)$$

3.4.3.-Cooling

In case of using the steam turbine, cooling is required to condense the steam. For small facilities ponds are used.

3.5.- Solution procedure

The design problem is solved by minimizing a simplified profit function including the income provided by the limonene, the juice and the power and the cost of the utilities needed, eq. (8)

$$Z = C_{Lim}L + C_{juice}J + C_e \left(\sum_{i \in turbinebody} W_{(Turbine)} + W_{(GasTurb)} - \sum_{j \in compressors} W_{(compressors)} \right) - C_S \sum_{HX} S_{HX} \quad (8)$$

Subject to

- a) Oranges processing and juice pasteurization. Section 3.1
- b) Limonene extraction. Section 3.2
- c) Bioreactor model. Section 3.3
- d) Biogas purification. Section 3.4
- e) Bryaton cycle. Section 3.4.1
- f) Rankine cycle. Section 3.4.2

The superstructure of alternatives formulated as a mixed integer non linear problem (MINLP), is decomposed into four non linear programming problems (NLP), one per each limonene extraction technology and one per thermodynamic cycle. Table 2 shows the problem sizes. The main variables are the biogas and digestate compositions, the operating conditions at the gas turbine, inlet and outlet pressure, and the temperatures, and the pressures, temperatures and flows in the regenerative Rankine cycle. Most of the other variables are computed based on the ratios defined along the process model description.

Table 2.- Problem sizes for the four cases of study

	Hexane		Steam	
	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle
Equations	1227	1676	1692	1243
Variables	2050	2838	2881	2093

After the optimization, heat is integrated so that the energy available within the thermal cycles is used for the pasteurization of the juice. Next, the investment and production costs are estimated. The investment cost of the facility is based on the factorial method³⁸ where the cost for the different units is estimated by updating the values computed using the correlations developed in previous work.³⁹ The estimation of the investment cost is performed assuming that the plant processes fluids and slurries. For the production cost, again, the factorial method is used.³⁸ The cost of the oranges for juice is taken to be 0.1 €/kg⁴⁰ the cost of steam 0.019 €/kg⁴¹ and that of cooling water 0.00057 €/kg,⁴² while the fresh hexane cost is taken to be 1.5 €/kg⁴³

4.-Results

The results are divided into the summary of the operation of the different alternative processes and the evaluation of their economics. As a basis, a flowrate of oranges of 5 kg/s is assumed. It is a value close to the production of Murcia and one tenth of the production in the Comunidad Valenciana, the largest producer in Spain.⁴⁴ A scale down/up study is carried out to evaluate the economics and find the minimum plant capacity that allows profitability.

4.1.-Mass and energy balances

Table 3 summarizes the major operating conditions of the four alternatives, per limonene recovery process and per thermodynamic cycle from biogas, either gas turbine or a combined cycle to process 5 kg/s of oranges.

The use of hexane to recover the limonene differs from the steam explosion process mainly in the consumption of chemicals and utilities. The use of steam decreases the need for utilities. Only around 3 MW of steam are required, and there is no need for heating up the feed to the digester since the products from the flash are already above the digester temperature. In the case of using hexane, the recovery of steam requires a large amount of steam, around 11 MW, which results in larger utilities consumption.

The use of the waste once limonene has been recovered follows an anaerobic digestion. The biogas composition and flow is the same in all cases. Note that the possible inhibition due to the presence of hexane in the waste is not considered. However, the main difference between the use of hexane or steam explosion is the fact that when using steam a larger flow is processed since a fraction of the steam remains as water with the peels. The advantage is that this stream does not need to be heated up for digestion, it is already at a high temperature, but the number of digestors for the same initial flow of oranges is 3 instead of just 2. The digestate contains a larger carbon to nitrogen ratio than the one expected as fertilizer, typically around 20, and low nutrient content, but it can be complemented with other sources.

It is possible to see that the gas turbine and the combined cycle operate similarly, independently of the pretreatment. However, while the use of a gas turbine allows energy to be integrated for the pasteurization process, so that it is self-sustained, the use of a combined cycle produces twice the power, see also Table 3. 4.2 GWh can be produced if a gas turbine is used (510 kW), that can easily satisfy the 35 kW consumed by the plant. In the case of using a combined cycle, 8.8 GWh can be produced (1048 kW). Another interesting result is the different operating conditions of the gas turbine if it operates within a combined cycle compared to its stand alone operation. In this last case, the gas turbine uses a smaller pressure ratio, 4, compared to the one used within a combined cycle, 6.3. The operating conditions of the steam turbine are typical, see Table 2, and similar to the ones in a previous study for a CSP facility.³⁷

The energy integration is different per alternative limonene recovery technology and power cycle. In case of using a gas turbine, the hot flue gas is capable of providing the thermal energy required for pasteurization in full. If the limonene is recovered using hexane, its condensation can be used to partially heat up the stream that feeds the stripping column. When using steam explosion it is possible to use energy to save in the production of the steam fed to the pretreatment. In case of using the combined cycle, the availability of energy in the flue gas is

far smaller, 25% of the one when the gas turbine is used. As a result, for the processes using a combined cycle the thermal energy to be purchased is higher than for those using the gas turbine, as it can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3.- Major operating conditions of the processes

	Hexane		Steam	
	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle
Juice Production				
Juice (kg/s)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Juice m ³ /yr	77760	77760	77760	77760
Limonene extraction				
Hexane added (kg/s)	30	30	NA	NA
Steam used (kg/s)	NA	NA	1.125	1.125
Limonene (kg/kgPeel)	0.021 519 t/yr	0.021 519 t/yr	0.023 519 t/yr	0.023 519 t/yr
Waste digestion				
N of digesters	2	2	3	3
Biogas produced kg /kg of peel	0.115	0.115	0.115	0.115
Biogas Composition	67.5% CH ₄ ; 30% CO ₂ ; 2% N ₂ ; 0.5% O ₂ ; 0.001 % H ₂ S; 0.009% NH ₃	67.5% CH ₄ ; 30% CO ₂ ; 2% N ₂ ; 0.5% O ₂ ; 0.001 % H ₂ S; 0.009% NH ₃	67.5% CH ₄ ; 30% CO ₂ ; 2% N ₂ ; 0.5% O ₂ ; 0.001 % H ₂ S; 0.009% NH ₃	67.5% CH ₄ ; 30% CO ₂ ; 2% N ₂ ; 0.5% O ₂ ; 0.001 % H ₂ S; 0.009% NH ₃
Fertilizer kg dry /kg of peel	0.649 (Water 0.229)	0.649 (Water 0.229)	0.652 (Water , 0.234)	0.652 (Water , 0.234)
NPK index	0.62/0.37/0.87	0.62/0.37/0.87	0.62/0.37/0.87	0.62/0.37/0.87
RNC	51.5	51.5	51.5	51.5
Power production				
Gas turbine				
Power (kW)	510	637	510	636
Pin/Pout	4	6.3	4	6.3
Steam turbine				
Power (kW)	NA	412	NA	412
HP, MP, LP, Exhaust (bar)	NA	125/29/5/0.08	NA	125/29/5/0.08
Power produced GWh	4.2	8.8	4.2	8.8
Power consumption				
Oranges processing (kW)	9	9	9	9

Gas clean up (kW)	26	26	26	26
Thermal Utilities				
Cooling (MW)	10.6	11.1	2.1	2.3
Steam (MW)	10.9	11.7	2.7	2.9

4.2.-Economic evaluation

The economic evaluation includes the estimation of the investment cost of the four alternatives as well as the production costs to compare them in detail. The annual profit after taxes is computed as follows:

$$Profit = \frac{0.75(Sales - Costs)}{Investment} \cdot 100 \quad (9)$$

Finally, the importance of the scale of the facility in the decision on the amount of oranges to process is assessed by means of a scale up/down study that evaluates both the investment and production costs as a function of the processing capacity of oranges.

4.2.1.- Investment cost

Table 4 shows the investment cost of the four different alternatives. It can be seen that the use of hexane results in a lower investment cost. This is due to the fact that in the case of using steam explosion, a fraction of the steam and water fed to the limonene removal stage remains with the organic matter and it is fed into the digester. As a result, a larger number of reactors are required to process the same amount of orange waste. Figure 5 shows the breakdown of the cost of the processes. Two main facts can be highlighted. The digester shows the largest contribution to the investment of the process. The second largest typically corresponds to the heat exchanger network. In the case of using the combined cycle, all the HX's involved are included not in the section corresponding to the gas and steam turbines sector but within the HX's and they represent one third of the equipment costs. The section devoted to the recovery of limonene represents a small fraction, 2-5%, while the production of the juice represents around 10%. This analysis explains the fact that waste is typically not further processed within juice production industries. This section would represent around 85% of the cost.

Table 4. Summary of the economic evaluation of the 4 alternatives

	Hexane		Steam	
	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle	Gas Turbine	Combined Cycle
Investment (M€)	33	45	47	61
Production costs (M€/yr)	34	35	23	26

Profit	119%	85%	100%	76%
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Figure 5.- Breakdown of the investment in units per alternative a) Hexane GT; b) Hexane CC; c) Steam GT; d) Steam CC

4.2.2.- Production cost

Table 3 presents the production costs of the four alternatives and Figure 6 shows the breakdown of the costs per item. The items included are the raw materials, the oranges, salaries, considered to be those corresponding to the jobs generated at the facility, 0.57 jobs/M€ invested,⁴⁵ equipment amortization, based on the plant life, administration and other expenses, in all cases 2.5 M€/yr each are assumed, and the utilities that are computed in the process analysis. Note that heat integration is performed to improve the efficiency of the facility. The power consumption is covered internally. Within the chemicals, the make-up of hexane is accounted for. In

all alternatives the largest contribution to the cost corresponds to the oranges, representing above 45% of the production costs. In the case of using hexane to recover the limonene, the production costs are 50% above those when steam is used. This is due to the need for hexane and the fact that the recovery of hexane is highly energy intense so that the utilities represent 10% of the cost. In the case of using steam, the consumption of utilities goes down to 4%. The steam required to operate the system is 25% the one required for operating the facilities that use a pretreatment using hexane, and the energy can be better integrated. The flash that recovers part of the steam sends the feedstock to the digester already above the temperature of operation, saving heating energy.

Figure 6.- Breakdown of the production costs of the different alternatives. a) Hexane GT; b) Hexane CC; c) Steam GT; d) Steam CC

Comparing the profitability, the lower investment required by the hexane results in more profitable processes, see Table 4. However, note that the production costs are far larger, up to 50% higher, than using hexane. Furthermore, there is a risk that the presence of traces of hexane critically reduce the yield of the anaerobic digestion as well as the fact that limonene contains traces of hexane preventing its use in certain industries. Note that the selling price for juice is considered to be 1€/kg. However, the actual price can be from 0.4 €/L in origin up to 3.4 €/L at the supermarket.⁴⁶ Therefore, the profit can drop by 75% with respect the one

presented in Table 4 if the juice price goes to the minimum. In addition, the cost of the oranges can go up to 0.8€/kg,⁴⁷ in which case the selling price of the juice must reach 1.6€/kg to cover the costs. It is possible to see that the volatility in the prices may result in high gains or even losses.

4.2.3.-Scale studies

Although the transport of oranges is relatively easy compared to shipping waste or energy crops, the scale of the facility determines its profitability. The procedure for the scale-up of chemical facilities was described in previous work.^{48,49} The cost of the units is a function of the flow they process, energy or mass flow. Using the proper cost correlations, including the fact that the size of the units also determines the cost correlation to use and the need to duplicate the units if their size goes beyond the standard, the investment cost is estimated as a function of the processing capacity. The effect of the scale on the production cost is easier to compute, since most of the items are directly related to the mass and energy balances, and they are proportional to the scale, while the rest are a function of the investment cost. Figures 7 and 8 show the investment and production cost of the facilities evaluated as a function of the oranges processed per year. It is possible to see that there are discontinuities due to the need to use another digester to process the waste. Two or three of these discontinuities are found for the use of hexane or steam explosion respectively due to the largest flow of waste generated using steam explosion. As a result, the investment cost is always larger in the case of using steam explosion. However, the production costs are far lower in the case of using this last pretreatment, due to the better integration and lower energy consumption, see Figure 8. Because of the lower production costs, the size of the plant that shows a positive profit is smaller, from 40 kt/yr the facility that uses steam already becomes profitable. Furthermore, the production costs of the combined cycle are larger because of the maintenance of the regenerative Rankine cycle to be maintained.

Figure 7.- Effect of the scale on the investment cost of integrated plants for juice production. Hex: Hexane pretreatment; Sexp: Steam explosion; CC: Combined cycle; GT: gas turbine

Figure 8.- Effect of the scale on the production costs of integrated plants for juice production. Hex: Hexane pretreatment; Sexp: Steam explosion; CC: Combined cycle; GT: gas turbine

5.-Conclusions

In this work, an integrated facility that processes oranges is optimized for the production of juice, and the processing of the peels to obtain added value products such as limonene and power. Two different limonene production technologies, hexane extraction and steam explosion, and two thermal cycles, a gas turbine and a combined cycle are evaluated. The units are modelled one by one based on first principles. The flowsheet model

has been formulated as an MINLP that is solved as four different NLP's, one per topology configuration and an economic evaluation of the alternatives is performed.

The use of steam explosion results in 50% lower production costs. The process is better energy integrated and requires lower amount of utilities. However, the larger flow of waste to be processed requires 1 additional digester that increases the investment costs by 25%. The use of hexane is more energy demanding and may leave hexane residues the biomass not adequate for its digestion, but the investment is lower resulting in better profits. As a result, the steam based facilities are profitable at lower production capacities; above 40kt/yr. Combined cycles are less profitable due to the additional investment. Based on the results presented, use of steam explosion and the installation of a gas turbine is the recommended set of technologies to improve the sustainability of this industry. By including the waste processing into the juice industry, the facility does not only remain profitable, due to the high price of limonene, but also the circular economy concept reduces the residue and the external energy consumption providing additional byproducts of added value such as fertilizers.

Nomenclature

C_i : Cost of item i , i belongs to { e: electricity; L: limonene; j: juice}
 k : polytropic coefficient.
 K_{index} : Potassium index of fertilizer.
 $fc_{(j)}$: Mass flow of component J from unit to unit1 (kg/s)
 H_j : Enthalpy of the stream j (kJ/kg).
 MW : Molar mass.
 N_{index} : Nitrogen index of fertilizer.
 $P_{in/compressor}$: Inlet pressure to compressor (bar).
 $P_{out/compressor}$: Outlet pressure of compressor (bar).
 P_{index} : Phosphorous index of fertilizer.
 R_{C-N} : Carbon to nitrogen molar ratio
 T_j : Temperature of the stream j (°C)
 $T_{in/compressor}$: Inlet temperature to compressor (°C).
 $T_{out/compressor}$: Outlet temperature of compressor (°C).
 V_{biogas} : Biogas volume produced per unit of volatile solids (VS) ($m^3_{biogás}/kg_{VS}$).
 W : Power produced or consumed (kW)
 w_{DM} : dry mass fraction (kg_{DM}/kg).
 w'_{VS} : dry mass fraction of volatile solids out of the dry mass (kg_{VS}/kg_{DM}).
 w'_{Nam} : dry mass fraction of Nam (inorganic nitrogen) (kg_{Nam}/kg_{DM}).
 w'_{Norg} : dry mass fraction of Norg(organic nitrogen) (kg_{Norg}/kg_{DM}).
 w'_P : dry mass fraction of P (kg_P/kg_{DM}).
 w'_K : dry mass fraction of K (kg_K/kg_{DM}).
 w'_{Resk} : dry mass fraction of the rest of the elements contained in k (kg_K/kg_{MS}).
 $W_{(unit)}$: Power produced or consumed in unit (kW).
 Z : Objective function.

Symbols and Constants:

η_c : Compressor's efficiency.
 η_s : Isentropic efficiency (0.9)
R: Ideal gas constant= 8.314 J/mol.K.

Equipment and others:

Src1= Source

Src2= Source .

Snki= Sink *i* of stream.

Bioreactor= Digester.

Compressi= Gas compressor *i*.

Flash: Flash

HXi= Heat exchanger *i*.

Mill: Milling unit

Reacti: Reactor *i*

Spli= Splitter *i*.

Mixi=Mixer *i*.

Sepi=Separator *i*.

Tanki: Tank *i*

MSi= Molecular sieve *i*.

Supporting Information

Additional modeling details can be found in the supporting information. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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